

Supplementary Material

The socio-ecological system described by the extracted metrics

Table A1: Elements and sub-elements of the socio-ecological system

Elements	Subelements	Description
Biodiversity	State of biodiversity	Status of populations, communities and/or species.
	Change in biodiversity	Change or trends in populations, communities and/or species
	Genetic resources	Information, access and/or safehouse of species genetic resources
	Genetic diversity	Phylogenetics, genetic diversity
	Species conservation	Species conservation status and/or action. Includes any mention to wildlife management policies
Ecosystems	State of ecosystems (coverage)	Extent of natural ecosystems (this sub-category is only applied to terrestrial ecosystems)
	State of ecosystems (configuration)	Configuration (fragmentation, connectivity) of natural ecosystems (this sub-category is only applied to terrestrial ecosystems)
	State of ecosystems (integrity)	Integrity (quality) of natural ecosystems (this sub-category is only applied to terrestrial ecosystems)
	State of ecosystems (marine)	Extent, configuration, and quality of marine ecosystems
	State of ecosystems (freshwater/coastal)	Extent, configuration, and quality of freshwater and coastal ecosystems
	State of ecosystems	Extent, configuration, and quality of ecosystems where no realm or other differentiation was done
	Change in ecosystems	Changes or trends in natural ecosystems
	Area conservation	Measures of protected areas, OECMs and indigenous lands. Includes any mention of land management and planning (e.g. green or blue urban spaces)

	Restoration efforts	Status of restoration or regeneration activities.
	Abiotic conditions	Temperature, precipitation, soil, water, air, sunlight (status and change)
Ecosystem services	Specific mention of sustainable use of species/ecosystems	Sustainable use of Nature
	Specific monetary valuation of nature contribution	Economic valuation of ecosystem services
	Nature contribution	Nature's Contribution to people (i.e., ecosystem services) with no differentiation between sustainable/unsustainable use or monetary/intrinsic values
Human well-being	Wellness	Descriptions of happiness, general human wellness (holistic indicators)
	Healthy living conditions	Metrics of environmental conditions required for a healthy livelihood
	Cultural diversity	Descriptions of race and ethnicity diversity, identity
	Equity	Metrics related to equality of gender, age and disability, justice and freedom of choice, land tenure rights
	Recreation	Recreation in the broadest sense (including alcohol use)
Direct drivers	Land conversion	Metrics on habitat loss, land use change
	Pollution	Measurements of air and/or water pollution
	Specific mention of over-exploitation and unsustainable use of species/ecosystems	Over-exploitation and unsustainable use of Nature (explicitly unsustainable or illegal), trade of threatened species, human footprint and food waste.
	Climate change	Metrics of emissions, fossil-fuel use, climate change and their effects
	Invasive alien species	Introductions, establishments, spread and impacts of invasive alien species
	(Infectious) diseases	Spread of infectious diseases, hosts, vectors, zoonoses, and infectious diseases
	Natural drivers	Natural disasters or extreme weather events

Human assets	State of economy	Financial assets such as investments, loans, GDP
	Income	Employment, access to jobs, fellowships, benefits
	Infrastructure (build-up area)	Metrics on human infrastructure (e.g., build-up area, roads, hydroelectric developments, energy production)
	Coverage of basic needs	Access to food, drinking/potable water, education, healthcare, housing (including metrics on consumption)
Knowledge systems	Information on biodiversity	Information status on biodiversity (data on species, number of assessments, and knowledge gaps)
	Information on society and socio-economics	Information status on social aspects (population trends, growth, etc.)
	Specific information on ILK and IPLC	Information status on indigenous and local communities (IPLC areas, indigenous peoples' populations)
	Specific information on human-nature relationship	Actions describing people living in harmony with nature (recycling programs, environmental education)
	ILK	Indigenous local knowledge (local calendar, artisanal management, linguistics)
Governance	Legislation/governance	Descriptions of institutions and governance systems
	Nature-based funding	Programs involving funding for conservation/restoration/climate change
	Nature-based legislation	Legislation that supports nature-based and climate mitigation solutions
	Nature detrimental legislation	Legislation that supports extractive and non-sustainable activities
	Legislation regarding ILK and IPLC	Legislation on ILC
	National/international cooperation	International legislation, multilateral cooperation and agreements (e.g., migration treaties). Includes any capacity building effort.
	Broken governance	Measurements of corruption, broken laws, violence, assault, injustice

Table A2: Elements of the socio-ecological system assessed in assessments and MEAs.

Elements	Number of metrics	Proportion of metrics
Biodiversity	190	10.39
Ecosystems	518	28.32
Ecosystem services	122	6.67
Human well-being	140	7.65
Direct drivers	222	12.14
Human assets	169	9.24
Knowledge systems	209	11.43
Governance	259	14.16

Table A3: Elements of the socio-ecological system assessed by source.

Elements	IPBES	IPCC	GEO	GBF	SDG	RAMSAR	CITES	CMS	UNCCD
Biodiversity	126	9	17	53	4	2	2	8	1
Ecosystems	97	308	50	70	10	13	0	3	3
Ecosystem services	80	8	15	23	6	2	2	1	0
Human well-being	61	2	38	22	40	1	0	0	2
Direct drivers	117	43	51	33	16	1	0	0	0
Human assets	94	3	23	15	90	0	0	0	1
Knowledge systems	124	2	15	25	28	15	9	5	0
Governance	98	1	10	70	46	31	39	8	6

Table A4: Sub-elements of the socio-ecological system assessed by source.

Elements	Subelements	IPBES	IPCC	GEO	GBF	SDG	RAMSAR	CITES	CMS	UNCCD
Biodiversity	Change in biodiversity	17	1	2	2	0	2	1	4	1
	Genetic diversity	5	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	0
	Genetic resources	4	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0
	Species conservation	6	0	0	8	1	0	1	0	0
	State of biodiversity	94	8	15	36	2	0	0	4	0
Ecosystems	Abiotic conditions	12	257	22	2	0	0	0	0	0
	Area conservation	21	0	4	17	3	7	0	2	0
	Change in ecosystems	10	11	7	7	2	1	0	1	2
	State of ecosystems	30	31	13	25	2	0	0	0	0
	State of ecosystems (configuration)	2	1	0	3	0	0	0	0	0
	State of ecosystems (coverage)	14	2	2	4	2	0	0	0	0

	State of ecosystems (freshwater/coastal)	2	2	1	4	0	0	0	0	0
	State of ecosystems (integrity)	3	0	1	6	0	2	0	0	1
	State of ecosystems (marine)	3	4	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
	Restoration efforts	0	0	0	2	0	3	0	0	0
Ecosystem services	Nature contribution	59	8	9	10	2	0	0	0	0
	Specific mention of sustainable use of species/ecosystems	10	0	5	11	2	2	1	1	0
	Specific monetary valuation of nature contribution	11	0	1	2	2	0	1	0	0
Human well-being	Equity	15	1	3	13	24	0	0	0	0
	Healthy living conditions	28	1	35	5	11	1	0	0	2
	Recreation	7	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
	Wellness	11	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0
	Cultural diversity	0	0	0	3	1	0	0	0	0

Direct drivers	(Infectious) diseases	3	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
	Climate change	9	26	5	5	2	0	0	0	0
	Invasive alien species	37	0	0	5	0	1	0	0	0
	Land conversion	12	0	6	3	2	0	0	0	0
	Natural drivers	6	10	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
	Pollution	28	7	36	14	5	0	0	0	0
	Specific mention of over-exploitation and unsustainable use of species/ecosystems	22	0	3	4	5	0	0	0	0
Human assets	Coverage of basic needs	26	0	8	3	40	0	0	0	0
	Income	15	0	3	6	10	0	0	0	0
	Infrastructure (build-up area)	30	2	7	3	19	0	0	0	0
	State of economy	23	1	5	3	21	0	0	0	1
Knowledge systems	ILK	45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Information on biodiversity	18	0	0	7	0	5	3	2	0
	Information on society and socio-economics	36	0	8	9	26	1	0	1	0

	Specific information on ILK and IPLC	6	0	0	4	0	1	1	1	0
	Specific information on human-nature relationship	19	2	7	5	2	8	5	1	0
Governance	Broken governance	2	0	0	1	2	0	2	0	0
	Legislation/governance	22	1	3	8	15	0	1	0	0
	National/international cooperation	12	0	1	10	6	17	21	0	3
	Nature detrimental legislation	4	0	3	3	1	0	0	0	0
	Nature-based funding	20	0	0	15	6	3	2	1	3
	Nature-based legislation	38	0	3	33	16	11	13	7	0